

Predictors of change in cocaine use in a street-recruited cohort of young cocaine users

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ABSTRACT

Aim To determine predictors of changes in amount of cocaine use among regular users outside treatment services. **Design** Longitudinal study—we estimated the proportion of subjects who increased or decreased cocaine use and assessed possible predictors related to these changes among a street-recruited cohort of young regular cocaine users (RCU). **Setting** Three Spanish cities: Barcelona, Madrid and Seville **Participants** A total of 720 RCU aged 18–30 years not regularly using heroin were recruited in the community during 2004–06 (Itinere Project). Follow-up interviews ($n = 501$) were carried out at 12–24 months. **Measurements** The average amount of cocaine used weekly was calculated taking into account the number of days of use and the usual quantity (g/day). A multinomial logistic regression approach was used to investigate the association between changes in amount of cocaine use (i.e. difference exceeded 33.3% of baseline level) after 12–24 months, and baseline socio-demographic characteristics, nightlife, patterns of cocaine use and use of alcohol and other psychoactive drugs. **Findings** Cocaine use baseline average level was 2.14 g/week [95% confidence interval (CI) = 2.02–2.42]. It decreased in 71.5% of subjects and increased in 14.1%. In multinomial analysis, negative associations were found between decreasing cocaine use and high levels of alcohol consumption and using an increasing number of psychoactive drugs. Moreover, low education level, having used cocaine frequently in houses and reporting cocaine binges were associated with increasing cocaine use. **Conclusions** A street-recruited cohort of cocaine users in Spain showed a significant reduction in cocaine use over a period of 12–24 months. High consumption of alcohol and increasing use of other psychoactive drugs decreased the probability of reducing cocaine use.

Keywords Cocaine, cocaine-related disorders, epidemiology, natural drug use trajectories, prospective studies, substance abuse.

INTRODUCTION

In Europe, in 2012 the average prevalence of cocaine use in the last year among young people aged 15–34 years was 2.1% (approximately 3 million people), the highest prevalences in the world being for Spain (4.4%) and

the United Kingdom (4.2%) [1]. The number of new admissions to treatment for cocaine use has risen considerably in recent years [1]; approximately 67 000 subjects currently receive treatment for cocaine dependence. However, we know from studies targeting cocaine users that there is an important group of habitual users who are well integrated in society (characterized mainly by snorting, and not consuming opiates) who hardly have contact with health services [1–6]. Given that the health burden associated with cocaine use is increasing (in Spain for example, cocaine is the most commonly mentioned substance in emergencies directly related with drug use [7]), it is important to have longitudinal studies which examine the evolution and changes of cocaine consumption in this group of subjects.

Few studies are available in the literature based on socially integrated habitual cocaine users [2–4,8]. Recruitment of a sample which includes these subjects is not an easy task. Indeed, they may be considered a ‘hidden population’ for whom the small financial incentive normally offered is not sufficient compensation [6,9]. There are also studies with cocaine users who have never injected or who have not done so recently [4,10,11]. However, most participants in these studies (at least those recruited in developed countries) are mainly heroin users who also take cocaine. This group of cocaine users has social characteristics and drug use patterns which are radically different from those who do not use opiates [1,4,9]: they have a profile of social deprivation, a history of social conflict and tend to take cocaine more by smoking.

Little is known about cocaine use careers among users who have little contact with health services. Moreover, the few studies available targeted specific groups of users, such as injecting drug users [12–14], crack-cocaine smokers [15,16] or club-drug-using gay and bisexual men [17]. Longitudinal studies which have examined the evolution of cocaine use based on subjects in treatment are the most common [18–29]. However, they fail to be representative of the cocaine-using population, because obviously they collect information only about those who admit to having used cocaine, and also they only examine factors associated with cessation of cocaine use (or with ‘relapse’) without considering those who increase their consumption.

How cocaine use is measured is critical. To date, the usual practice has been to measure frequency of use (usually in terms of the number of days or lines per week, per month, year, etc.) without taking into account the average amount used. Both measures tell us about intensity of use. Failing to take both aspects into account, particularly when measuring changes over time, can lead to incorrect estimates of the true consumption or its variation.

Using data from a cohort of regular cocaine users, recruited in the street using targeted sampling and chain-referral methods and independently of the health services (Itinere Project), the aim of this study was to estimate the proportion of subjects who had increased, maintained or reduced the use of cocaine 12–24 months later, and to assess baseline and follow-up factors related to these changes.

METHODS

Participants and recruitment

The study was based on data from a cohort study of young regular current cocaine users recruited in the community, independently of the health services in three Spanish cities: Barcelona, Madrid and Seville (Itinere Project). Inclusion criteria for the study were age between 18 and 30 years, having resided in one of the cities and having used cocaine at least 50 days in the last 12 months (regular cocaine use) and on at least 1 day in the last 3 months (current cocaine use). They were also required not to have used heroin on more than 12 days in the last year to avoid attracting frequent heroin users who were also cocaine users.

A total of 720 participants were recruited by targeted sampling [30] and chain referral methods [31] between January 2004 and July 2006. Non-probabilistic techniques were used: (i) directly active searching in different

settings where cocaine users were likely to be found (recruiting 9% of the sample); (ii) indirectly active searching through key people, such as staff of harm reduction programmes and ex-users or users who did not meet the inclusion criteria (13.5%); (iii) passive reception of participants through advertisements in the media (8.3%); and (iv) the snowball method (69.2%). In an attempt to achieve representativeness, many scenarios were identified but few subjects were selected from each. Recruitment from drug dependence treatment services was avoided. Additional details on recruitment procedures and baseline characteristics of participants have been published elsewhere [6,9,32]. Participants had to sign an informed consent document approved by the Ethics Committee of the Instituto de Salud Carlos III. Follow-up interviews were scheduled at 12 months. Five hundred and one individuals were recruited from 715 potential participants [70.1%; 95% confidence interval (CI) = 66.4–73.5%] between September 2005 and October 2007, as five subjects had died (mortality data were confirmed by the Spanish National Statistics Institute [33]). The median follow-up time was 458 days (15 months). Each participant received €18 at the end of every interview.

Data collection

A computer-assisted personal interview (CAPI) was conducted using a mostly pre-coded questionnaire with some open questions [34–36]. It was applied in different health centres not dedicated specifically to drug problems by previously trained workers. The questionnaire covered in considerable detail the aspects included in the present analysis: socio-demographic characteristics, social conflict, nightlife, patterns of cocaine use and other psychoactive substances, use of health services, mental health disorders and sociometric scales to measure subjective perception of self-reported cocaine dependence [Severity of Dependence Scale (SDS) [37]] and health-related quality of life (Nottingham Health Profile [38]). Most of the questions referred to the last 12 months.

Measures

Changes in cocaine use between baseline and follow-up were assessed by comparing the amount of all types and routes of cocaine consumed: in the 12 months prior to the first interview, and during the follow-up period. Weekly consumption in each period was obtained by multiplying the average grams of cocaine consumed per day of use by the number of days of use, and dividing by the number of weeks in the period. The differences in weekly consumption between the two periods were grouped into three categories: ‘less cocaine use’ or ‘more cocaine use’ (when the difference exceeded 33.3% of the baseline level), and ‘similar cocaine use’ otherwise. This three-category variable representing ‘evolution of overall cocaine use’ was used as the dependent variable in a regression model. The cut-off at 33.3% corresponded to two standard deviations in the baseline distribution of weekly cocaine consumption levels. ‘Cocaine binge’ was defined as an episode of intensive cocaine use in a short period of time during which the quantity of cocaine used was higher than usual, with at least 6 hours without using cocaine after the binge episode.

Regarding alcohol, information about the number of standard drinks consumed during weekdays and weekend days was converted into ml/day of pure alcohol. The latter variable was recoded into three categories: ‘none or moderate consumption’ (<50 ml/day for men and <25 ml/day for women), ‘risk consumption’ (50–100 ml/day for men and 25–50 ml/day for women) and ‘high-risk consumption’ (>100 ml/day for men and >50 ml/day for women) [39].

Frequency categories of partying at weekends and on weekdays were dichotomized (‘every weekend’ versus ‘not every weekend’; and for weekdays ‘≥3 days a month’ versus ‘<3 days a month’). A participant was considered to have changed their frequency of partying if the value was categorized differently between baseline and follow-up.

Data analysis

First, we compared two subgroups: participants who were interviewed in the second visit (follow-up participants: FP) and those who were not interviewed (non-follow-up participants: NFP), in terms of several socio-

demographic characteristics, patterns of cocaine use and other baseline variables. Then, among FP, socio-demographic characteristics, nightlife, usage patterns of cocaine and other substances and mental health disorders were compared by evolution of overall cocaine use. Variables considered included both baseline and follow-up characteristics as well as some changes between follow-up and baseline. All comparisons were carried out using Pearson's χ^2 and Fisher's exact tests for categorical variables and analyses of variance (ANOVA) for continuous variables.

A multinomial logistic regression approach was used to investigate the association between relevant variables and the evolution of overall cocaine use after 12–24 months. The reference category was 'similar cocaine use'. The analysis was restricted to 488 individuals followed-up (97.4%), because 13 subjects had incomplete information about cocaine use frequency or amount at baseline or follow-up. This model was built based initially on those variables that showed a *P*-value < 0.20 in bivariate analyses (relevant variables) and then selecting significant variables after backwards elimination. Age, gender and city of residence were always included as adjusting factors. Goodness-of-fit was assessed using the Hosmer–Lemeshow test. PASW statistics version 18 was used for all analyses.

RESULTS

When the NFP and FP groups were compared, no significant differences were found for the majority of the socio-demographic variables, and none of the social conflict or nightlife variables (Table 1); nor were any found for cocaine use (in terms of either frequency or average amount) or in level of dependence assessed with SDS. However, differences were found for the consumption of crack cocaine (NFP: 33.5% versus FP: 17.4%), heroin use (NFP: 16.9% versus FP: 8.2%) and drug injection (NFP: 8.7% versus FP: 1.8%). NFP also presented worse health-related quality of life and a higher prevalence of acute health problems after using cocaine. Regarding services utilization, the NFP group presented a lower prevalence of non-emergency medical care and a higher prevalence of social needs. In both groups, very few subjects (5.9 and 4.4%) had received treatment for drug use in the last 12 months.

Most of the subjects followed-up (*n* = 349; 71.5%) had reduced their cocaine use before the second interview 12–24 months later, while 69 (14.1%) had increased use and 70 (14.3%) kept their use at similar levels. Among the subjects followed-up, the average level of cocaine use (crack and/or powder) in the 12 months prior to the baseline interview was 2.14 g/week (95% CI = 2.02–2.42) and in the follow-up interview this dropped to 1.05 g/week (95% CI = 0.87–1.23), representing a reduction of 50.9% (*P* < 0.001). The level of abstinence from cocaine use was low: 85 subjects (17.4%) had not used cocaine for at least 3 months prior to the follow-up interview, 45 (9.2%) for 6 months, and only seven (1.4%) had not consumed cocaine in the last 12 months.

Table 2 presents comparisons of the three categories of overall cocaine use evolution by different baseline, follow-up and combined variables. Differences were found for baseline educational level, employment status, most frequent place for cocaine use and reporting cocaine binges, as well as for levels of crack and alcohol use at follow-up. Changes between baseline and follow-up in the number of psychoactive drugs, SDS and partying frequency on weekdays were also statistically significant.

In multinomial logistic regression (Table 3), the factors associated with 'more cocaine use' were low educational level, using cocaine frequently at home or normal dwelling-place or friends' home, reporting cocaine binges and having increased the frequency of partying on weekdays. The probability of 'less cocaine use' was lower when living with a steady partner who was ever a regular cocaine user. Also, for each additional psychoactive substance other than cocaine which the subjects had used between the two interviews, the probability of reducing their cocaine use diminished (OR = 0.80; 95% CI = 0.69–0.94). This was also the case among those who had consumed high quantities of alcohol, with the lowest OR being found for high-risk consumers (OR = 0.23; 95% CI = 0.10–0.55).

Table 1 Socio-demographic characteristics, social conflict, patterns of cocaine use and other substances and use of health and social services at the baseline interview, by follow-up status.

	<i>Lost</i> (<i>n</i> = 219)		<i>Followed-up</i> (<i>n</i> = 501)		<i>Total participants</i> (<i>n</i> = 720)		<i>P-value</i>
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	
Socio-demographic characteristics							
City							
Barcelona	87	39.7	147	29.3	234	32.5	0.000
Madrid	87	39.7	171	34.1	258	35.8	
Seville	45	20.5	183	36.5	228	31.7	
Women	78	35.6	166	33.1	244	33.9	0.517
Foreigners	31	14.2	33	6.6	64	8.9	0.001
Age 25 years or less at baseline	156	71.2	387	77.2	543	75.4	0.085
Primary education or lower	98	44.7	203	40.5	301	41.8	0.290
Employment status ^a							0.000
Regularly employed	106	48.8	246	49.5	352	49.3	
Unemployed	83	38.2	111	22.3	194	27.2	
Studying	28	12.9	140	28.2	168	23.5	
Most income obtained from marginal or illegal activities ^a	45	20.5	91	18.2	136	18.9	0.467
Participant lives with							
Partner/children	41	19.1	59	11.8	100	14.0	0.002
Friends, room-mates, alone	71	33.0	134	26.9	205	28.8	
Parents/other relatives	103	47.9	305	61.2	408	57.2	
Living with a steady partner who was ever regular cocaine user	29	13.2	46	9.2	75	10.4	0.101
Having one or more children	11	5.0	13	2.6	24	3.3	0.095
Social conflict							
Ever left home for >2 days before age 18	63	28.8	121	24.2	184	25.6	0.191
Arrested ^a	44	20.1	88	17.6	132	18.3	0.420
Ever in prison	7	3.2	20	4.0	27	3.8	0.605
Assaulted ^a	46	21.0	119	23.8	165	22.9	0.412
Nightlife							
Partying every weekend ^a	165	75.7	388	77.4	553	76.9	0.607
Partying >3 weekdays a month ^a	142	65.1	309	61.7	451	62.7	0.378
Attending nightclubs or 'after-hours' > 52 times ^a	49	22.6	123	24.6	172	24.0	0.561
Attending 'raves' > 5 times ^a	59	27.2	163	32.6	222	31.0	0.150
Patterns of cocaine use							
Age first cocaine use [mean (SD)]	16.9	(2.5)	16.7	(2.2)	16.8	(2.3)	0.190
Average days of cocaine use [mean (SD)] ^a	142.9	(79.7)	132.7	(63.6)	135.8	(69.0)	0.158
Average quantity of cocaine use (g/week) [mean (SD)] ^a	2.4	(2.5)	2.1	(2.8)	2.2	(2.7)	0.082
Most frequent place of cocaine use ^a							
Home or normal dwelling place or friends' homes	71	32.4	154	30.8	225	31.3	0.312
Cars	26	11.9	85	17.0	111	15.4	
Open public places or places where drugs are sold and/or consumed	45	20.5	106	21.2	151	21.0	
Recreational areas: pubs, discos	77	35.2	155	31.0	232	32.3	
Main route of cocaine administration ^a							
Smoked or injected	29	13.3	29	5.8	58	8.1	0.002
Sniffed	189	86.7	471	94.2	660	91.9	
Crack cocaine use ^a	73	33.5	87	17.4	160	22.3	0.000
Reported cocaine binges ^{a,b}	144	65.8	340	67.9	484	67.2	0.579
Cocaine use-related health problems							
Acute health problems after using cocaine ^a	82	37.4	148	29.5	230	31.9	0.036
Level of cocaine dependence ^a [mean SDS score (SD)]	4.6	(3.3)	4.1	(2.8)	4.2	(3.0)	0.078
Other drugs use							
Average consumption of alcohol/day ^{a,c}							
None or moderate consumption	74	33.8	142	28.3	216	30.0	0.318
Risk consumption	73	33.3	174	34.7	247	34.3	
High-risk consumption	72	32.9	185	36.9	257	35.7	
Average number of psychoactive substances used ^d (excluding cocaine, alcohol and tobacco)	4.1	2.4	3.9	2.2	4.0	2.3	0.021
Heroin use ^a	37	16.9	41	8.2	78	10.8	0.001
Ever injected ^a	19	8.7	9	1.8	28	3.9	0.000
Use of social and health services							
Drug use treatment ^a	13	5.9	22	4.4	35	4.9	0.385
Admitted to hospital ^a	21	9.6	49	9.8	70	9.8	0.917
Received emergency medical care ^a	113	51.6	219	44.0	332	46.3	0.059
Received non-emergency medical care outside hospital or prison ^a	134	61.2	355	71.3	489	68.2	0.007
Attended by a family doctor ^a	103	47.0	290	58.2	393	54.8	0.005
Attended by a psychiatrist ^a	13	5.9	28	5.6	41	5.7	0.868
Attended by a social worker ^a	24	11.0	32	6.4	56	7.8	0.036
Sociometric scale							
Nottingham Health Profile ^d [mean score (SD)]	15.6	(16.9)	10.2	(12.0)	11.9	(13.9)	0.014

SD = standard deviation; SDS = Severity of Dependence Scale. ^aIn last 12 months. ^bIn the questionnaire a cocaine binge was defined as an episode of intensive cocaine use in a short period of time (hours or days), in which the quantity of cocaine used was higher than usual, with at least 6 hours without using cocaine after the binge episode. ^cModerate consumption = consumption <50 ml/day in men and 25 ml/day in women; risk consumption = 50–100 ml/day in men and 25–50 ml/day in women; high-risk consumption = consumption >100 ml/day in men and 50 ml/day in women. ^dThis Health-Related Quality of Life questionnaire consists of 38 items which measure five health dimensions (energy, pain, emotional reactions, sleep, social isolation and physical mobility); its total score ranges from 0 (best) to 100 (worst).

DISCUSSION

Our results show a significant reduction in the use of cocaine by a street-recruited cohort of young cocaine users after a period of 12–24 months had elapsed. However, an important part (almost 30%) continued to use it in similar or increased quantities. The proportion abstaining was relatively low: only one in 10 participants had been without consuming for 6 months, and almost none in the last year. We found negative associations between consuming large amounts of alcohol and increasing use of other psychoactive drugs, and the probability of reducing cocaine use. Subjects living with a steady partner who was ever a regular cocaine user also had a lower probability of reducing their cocaine use. Having a low educational level, having used cocaine mainly in houses, having reported cocaine binges in the baseline interview and having increased nightlife during weekdays were all associated with increased cocaine use.

One of the main strengths of the present study is that it is based on a cohort of young cocaine users who do not usually use heroin, recruited in the street; in other words, not in health services, from where most samples of cocaine users described in the literature have come [6].

The recruitment process attempted to achieve representativeness of all cocaine users by recruiting them in a variety of different settings and by various means, and considerable importance was given to nomination. Also, in order to estimate the changes in cocaine use over time, we took into account not only days of use (frequency) but also the average quantity used on a usual day of consumption (intensity). The opportunity to measure both dimensions made it possible to detect those users who maintained a similar frequency of consumption but had increased (28.7%) or decreased (29.5%) the usual amount, and vice versa, those who continued to use the same amount but with different frequencies (5.9 and 65.4%, respectively). The most important change was related to a decline in the frequency of use, rather than the quantity.

Several studies have shown that subjects with higher cocaine use are more likely to suffer cocaine-related disorders [40–42], but without giving precise quantities. Cocaine being an illegal substance makes it difficult to establish clinically relevant consumption variations. Our cut-off of a 33.3% change allowed estimating individual variations independently of the quantity used.

Our results are consistent with previous studies based on non-clinical samples of cocaine users which also show a significant reduction in cocaine use, although different results have been found depending on the type of cocaine mainly used by the recruited sample. In our sample, the main form of cocaine use was by snorting, crack use being fairly rare in Spain [7]. Samples involving powder cocaine users showed somewhat higher reductions (45%) in an observation period of 12 months [17], especially among those who, at some time in their lives, had been heavy users [43], or when a longer follow-up was considered [44]. One study [15] observed a 35% decrease of cocaine use among crack users over a period of 6 months. The reduction observed in the present study (50.9%), which includes both types of cocaine users, was higher than in the cohort of crack users. Among weekly crack users in the Itinere sample the reduction in cocaine use was lower (43.7%) than among participants who did not use crack (52.0%). These differences in cocaine use over time between powder cocaine and crack users are consistent with the literature, in which crack users are characterized by a more intense cocaine use and higher prevalence of other drug use and of injection [1,6].

One of our main findings was a negative association between a reduction of cocaine use 12–24 months later, and the increasing consumption of psychoactive substances other than cocaine and/or of high alcohol consumption. This is one of the few studies which clearly show the ‘braking effect’ of the use of other drugs on the probability of reducing cocaine use, an aspect which should be taken into account by preventive policies aimed at the user population, and particularly at those who are not under the supervision of health-care services, given that cocaine users exhibit a much more extensive use of alcohol, cannabis and ‘club drugs’ (designer drugs, amphetamines and hallucinogens) than the general population of the same age [1,2,4,6,45]. Our results also show a higher probability of cocaine use increasing among users who usually consumed in houses (i.e. at home or at a friend’s house) with respect to those who did so in bars or discos. There are two possible explanations for this: (i) being an illegal drug, it is more difficult to consume cocaine in party venues, where use must be clandestine; and (ii) in the process of cessation of cocaine use, some studies have shown the importance of certain social factors such as changes in consumption habits of close friends who are also users, or even in the number of them [12,13,46,47]. Being a substance normally consumed in a group setting, in the period of time evaluated (12–24 months) it is quite likely that the subjects were affected by changes of this type. Due to this leisure-time use of cocaine, it was not surprising to find an association between having an intense nightlife on weekdays and a rise in cocaine use. However, the multinomial model rejected the same variable when it referred to nightlife at

weekends. Perhaps this is due to the fact that, for practically all subjects, high levels of weekend nightlife were reported in both interviews, which was not the case for weekdays.

We explored several other variables among those reported to be related to changes in drug use, although none was specific for cocaine use. We did not find any association with having had acute health problems after using cocaine or social conflict. Regarding changes in roles or status, one study reported that users who stopped using cocaine were more likely to be married and have children [47]; we did not find such an association, probably because of small numbers. Some others, such as changes in friends' patterns of drug use or in their access to drugs [48,49], could not be explored in this study. However, we found an association between living with a steady partner who was ever a regular cocaine user and not reducing cocaine use.

Certain limitations should be borne in mind when interpreting the results of this study. We do not know to what extent the results may be generalized to young cocaine users, as we used non-probabilistic sampling [50]. The fact of eliciting personal contact details for follow-up and the inconvenience of having to travel about in a large city could have initially discouraged many users from participating in the study [6]. Additionally, as we have assumed, in many cases the financial incentive offered was not sufficient stimulus. However, this study represents clear improvements over many others in efforts to include drug users who are difficult to access by direct recruitment, and includes intense cocaine users not only from recreational settings. The intention of the Itinere Project was to change as little as possible the 'natural' drugs use trajectories and the health consequences for the participants, but it is not unreasonable to believe that participation in the survey itself could have influenced changes in cocaine use.

With regard to participants in the second interview, our follow-up figures are fairly similar to those of other studies based on cocaine users recruited in the community (68–71.3%) [15,17]. Making contact face to face, rather than by telephone, could have acted as a handicap with regard to encouraging subjects to participate in the second interview. Although we found hardly any differences in socio-economic characteristics or cocaine use patterns between FP and NFP, the differences found in crack and heroin use and injection, revealing a selective non-response, limit generalization of our results. However, as a result of this selective non-response, the follow-up sample would be more representative of cocaine users not consuming heroin, which was our primary goal, even though we lost some crack users.

With respect to data collection, self-reporting of drug use probably leads to underestimation of prevalence [51,52]. Although we took into account many variables related to different settings (social, drug use, mental and health problems, services utilization), the Itinere Project interview did not contemplate other important variables which could have influenced changes in use, such as changes in friends' cocaine use patterns [12,13,46,47] or having suffered some negative experience [47] (loss of job, death in the family). Another limitation relates to small numbers for some variables, such as previous treatment, making it impossible to test for an independent association of drug treatment with decreasing cocaine use [47].

This is one of the few studies which have examined the evolution of cocaine use in a sample including all types of cocaine users who do not normally consume heroin. Given that there are many habitual users of cocaine who never enter treatment, the factors found associated with increasing cocaine use have direct implications for possible public health interventions targeting specific groups of these users, particularly those with high consumption of alcohol and/or of other drugs. Even so, further longitudinal studies with longer follow-up are needed in order to elucidate the factors which induce users to give up their use of cocaine.

Table 2 Description of a cohort of young cocaine users, by overall evolution of cocaine use^a after 12–24 months; 2004–07.

	<i>More cocaine use</i>		<i>Similar cocaine use</i>		<i>Less cocaine use</i>		<i>Total participants</i>		<i>P-value</i>
	<i>n</i>	<i>%^b</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%^b</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%^b</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%^c</i>	
All subjects	69	14.1	70	14.3	349	71.5	488		
Socio-demographic characteristics									
City									0.082
Barcelona	23	16.3	23	16.3	95	67.4	141	28.9	
Madrid	27	16.4	28	17.0	110	66.7	165	33.8	
Seville	19	10.4	19	10.4	144	79.1	182	37.3	
Gender									0.149
Male	51	15.5	41	12.5	236	72.0	328	67.2	
Female	18	11.3	29	18.1	113	70.6	160	32.8	
Country of birth									0.561
Spain	64	14.0	64	14.0	330	72.1	458	93.9	
Other country	5	16.7	6	20.0	19	63.3	30	6.1	
Age at baseline									0.780
≤25 years	56	14.7	55	14.4	270	70.9	381	78.1	
>25 years	13	12.1	15	14.0	79	73.8	107	21.9	
Education level ^d									0.001
Primary education or lower	39	19.7	18	9.1	141	71.2	198	40.6	
Secondary education or higher	30	10.3	52	17.9	208	71.7	290	59.4	
Employment status ^d									0.034
Regularly employed	40	16.7	35	14.6	164	68.6	239	49.4	
Unemployed	19	17.8	17	15.9	71	66.4	107	22.1	
Studying	9	6.5	18	13.0	111	80.4	138	28.5	
Participant lives with ^d									0.141
Partner/children	8	13.6	14	23.7	37	62.7	59	12.2	
Friends, room-mates, alone	14	10.9	19	14.7	96	74.4	129	26.6	
Parents/other relatives	46	15.5	36	12.1	215	72.4	297	61.2	
Living with a steady partner who was ever regular cocaine user ^d									0.150
No	6	13.0	11	23.9	29	63.0	46	9.4	
Yes	63	14.3	59	13.3	320	72.4	442	90.6	
Social conflict									
Ever left home for >2 days before age 18									0.075
No	45	12.1	54	14.6	272	73.3	371	76.0	
Yes	24	20.5	16	13.7	77	65.8	117	24.0	
Assaulted ^d									0.125
No	47	12.7	58	15.7	265	71.6	370	76.0	
Yes	22	18.8	12	10.3	83	70.9	117	24.0	
Nightlife									
Partying at weekend ^d									0.859
Not every weekend	15	13.8	14	12.8	80	73.4	109	22.3	
Every weekend	54	14.2	56	14.8	269	71.0	379	77.7	
Partying on weekdays ^d									0.378
≤3 working days/month	31	16.5	29	15.4	128	68.1	188	38.5	
>3 working days/month	38	12.7	41	13.7	221	73.7	300	61.5	
Changes in frequency of going partying at weekends ^c									0.066
Less frequency	18	12.5	12	8.3	114	79.2	144	29.5	
Similar frequency	47	14.7	52	16.3	221	69.1	320	65.6	
More frequency	4	16.7	6	25.0	14	58.3	24	4.9	
Changes in frequency of going partying on weekdays ^c									0.000
Less frequency	24	8.7	33	12.0	219	79.3	276	57.0	
Similar frequency	21	18.8	21	18.8	70	62.5	112	23.1	
More frequency	24	25.0	15	15.6	57	59.4	96	19.8	

Table 2 *Cont.*

	More cocaine use		Similar cocaine use		Less cocaine use		Total participants		P-value
	n	% ^b	n	% ^b	n	% ^b	n	% ^c	
Patterns of cocaine use									
Age first cocaine use [mean (SD)]	16.2	(1.6)	16.7	(2.0)	16.9	(2.3)	17	(2.2)	0.059
Most frequent place of cocaine use ^d									0.012
Home or normal dwelling place or friends' homes	31	20.8	19	12.8	99	66.4	149	30.5	
Cars	14	16.5	11	12.9	60	70.6	85	17.4	
Open public places or places where drugs are sold and/or consumed	11	10.5	10	9.5	84	80.0	105	21.5	
Recreational areas: pubs, discos	13	8.7	30	20.1	106	71.1	149	30.5	
Crack cocaine use at follow-up visit									0.001
No	50	11.8	60	14.2	313	74.0	423	86.7	
Yes	19	29.2	10	15.4	36	55.4	65	13.3	
Reported cocaine binges ^{d,g}									0.006
No	14	8.9	32	20.3	112	70.9	158	32.4	
Yes	55	16.7	38	11.5	237	71.8	330	67.6	
Cocaine use-related health problems									
Acute health problems after using cocaine ^d									0.280
No	46	13.2	55	15.8	248	71.1	349	71.5	
Yes	23	16.5	15	10.8	101	72.7	139	28.5	
Level of cocaine dependence ^d [mean SDS score (SD)]	4.8	(3.3)	3.8	(2.4)	4.0	(2.8)	4.1	(2.8)	0.097
Difference in SDS-cocaine scores ^e [mean SDS score change (SD)]	0.0	(3.1)	-0.3	(1.9)	-1.4	(3.1)	-1.0	(3.0)	0.000
Other drugs use									
Average consumption of alcohol/day ^{d,f}									0.995
None or moderate consumption	20	14.4	19	13.7	100	71.9	139	28.5	
Risk consumption	24	14.1	26	15.3	120	70.6	170	34.8	
High-risk consumption	25	14.0	25	14.0	129	72.1	179	36.7	
Average consumption of alcohol/day at follow-up visit ^f									0.001
None or moderate consumption	26	12.0	17	7.9	173	80.1	216	44.3	
Risk consumption	27	14.2	35	18.4	128	67.4	190	38.9	
High-risk consumption	16	19.5	18	22.0	48	58.5	82	16.8	
Average number of psychoactive substances used ^d (excluding cocaine, alcohol and tobacco)	4.1	(2.3)	3.8	(2.0)	3.8	(2.2)	3.9	(2.2)	0.656
Difference in the number of psychoactive substances used (other than cocaine, alcohol and tobacco) ^e [mean difference (SD)]	0.7	(2.0)	0.3	(1.9)	-0.5	(1.8)	-0.2	(1.9)	0.000
Use of health services									
Ever drug use treatment									0.002
No	58	12.9	70	15.6	322	71.6	450	92.2	
Yes	11	28.9	0	0.0	27	71.1	38	7.8	
Received emergency medical care ^d									0.120
No	45	16.4	33	12.0	196	71.5	274	56.5	
Yes	24	11.4	36	17.1	151	71.6	211	43.5	
Sociometric scale									
Nottingham Health Profile ^h [mean score (SD)]	13.0	(15.2)	9.7	(11.5)	9.5	(11.1)	10	(11.9)	0.077

SD = standard deviation; SDS = Severity of Dependence Scale. ^a'Less cocaine use' or 'more cocaine use' indicate that the difference exceeded 33.3% of the baseline level. ^bThe percentages were calculated by rows. ^cThe percentages were calculated by columns. ^dIn last 12 months at baseline interview. ^eBetween baseline and follow-up interview. ^fModerate consumption = consumption <50 ml/day in men and 25 ml/day in women; risk consumption = 50–100 ml/day in men and 25–50 ml/day in women; high-risk consumption = consumption >100 ml/day in men and 50 ml/day in women. ^gIn the questionnaire a cocaine binge was defined as an episode of intensive cocaine use in a short period of time (hours or days) in which the quantity of cocaine used was higher than usual, with at least 6 hours without using cocaine after the binge episode. ^hThis Health-Related Quality of Life questionnaire consists of 38 items which measure five health dimensions (energy, pain, emotional reactions, sleep, social isolation and physical mobility); its total score ranges from 0 (best) to 100 (worst).

Table 3 Multinomial logistic regression analysis for changes in cocaine use between baseline and second visit in a cohort of young cocaine users in Spain, 2004–07^a.

	<i>More cocaine use versus similar cocaine use</i>		<i>Less cocaine use versus similar cocaine use</i>	
	<i>OR^b</i>	<i>CI^b (95%)</i>	<i>OR</i>	<i>CI (95%)</i>
Baseline variables				
Education level				
Secondary or highest	1.00		1.00	
Primary level or lower	3.64	(1.52–8.70)	1.69	(0.85–3.38)
Living with a steady partner who was ever regular cocaine user				
No	1.00		1.00	
Yes	0.34	(0.10–1.19)	0.29	(0.12–0.70)
Most frequent place of cocaine use in last 12 months				
Recreational areas: pubs, discos	1.00		1.00	
Home or normal dwelling place or friends' homes	5.94	(2.12–16.61)	1.76	(0.84–3.70)
Cars	2.82	(0.73–10.84)	1.08	(0.40–2.94)
Open public places or places where drugs are sold and/or consumed	2.12	(0.56–7.98)	1.91	(0.69–5.23)
Reported cocaine binges in last 12 months ^c				
No	1.00		1.00	
Yes	3.93	(1.57–9.82)	1.46	(0.77–2.73)
Follow-up variable				
Average consumption of alcohol/day ^d				
None or moderate consumption	1.00		1.00	
Risk consumption	0.47	(0.19–1.17)	0.32	(0.16–0.64)
High-risk consumption	0.61	(0.21–1.83)	0.23	(0.10–0.55)
Combined variables				
Changes in frequency of going partying on weekdays between baseline and second visit				
Less frequency	1.00		1.00	
Similar frequency	1.61	(0.64–4.03)	0.57	(0.29–1.15)
More frequency	3.09	(1.17–8.16)	0.73	(0.33–1.59)
Difference in the number of substances consumed (other than cocaine, alcohol and tobacco) between baseline and second visit				
Difference in SDS ^b cocaine scores between baseline and second visit	1.07	(0.94–1.22)	0.90	(0.80–1.00)
χ^2 Hosmer–Lemeshow test (<i>P</i> -value)	7.22	(0.514)	5.26	(0.729)

^aThe number of cases included in the logistic regression model was 488. 'Less cocaine use' or 'more cocaine use' indicate that the difference exceeded 33.3% of the baseline level. ^bOR = multinomial logistic regression odds ratio adjusted by all variables included in the table, plus sex, age and city of residence; CI = confidence interval; SDS: Severity of Dependence Scale. ^cIn the questionnaire a cocaine binge was defined as an episode of intensive cocaine use in a short period of time (hours or days) in which the quantity of cocaine used was higher than usual, with at least 6 hours without using cocaine after the binge episode. ^dModerate consumption = consumption <50 ml/day in men and 25 ml/day in women; risk consumption = 50–100 ml/day in men and 25–50 ml/day in women; high-risk consumption = consumption >100 ml/day in men and 50 ml/day in women.

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